

Substrate thickness variation on the frequency response of microstrip antenna for mm-wave application

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ABSTRACT

Substrate height (H_s) is an important parameter that influences antenna propagation. This research designed a low-profile 28 GHz microstrip antenna on a polyimide substrate with varying H_s using CST Studio software. The simulated results and MINITAB software were used to develop regression model equations, which analyzed the impact of H_s variation on the antenna performance. The proposed models' equations have indicated an increase in average responses of resonant frequency (F_r), percentage bandwidth (% BW), gain (G), return loss (RL), and efficiency (η) as the H_s decreased. The antenna achieved a BW of 3.87 GHz at H_s 0.525 mm and 5.54 GHz at 0.025 mm, a G of 3.89 dBi at H_s 0.525 mm and 3.91 dBi at H_s 0.025 mm, and an η of 94.19% at H_s 0.525 mm and 98.24% at H_s 0.025 mm. The antenna was fabricated and tested, and the experimental results were validated with the models' equations. The thinner substrate resulted in an improvement in the antenna performance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, wireless devices have become portable and require small antennas. Thus, substrate height (H_s) significantly impacts antenna portability and performance, as thinner substrate antennas are lightweight and portable [1]. The H_s employed propagation characteristics, such as electromagnetic field distribution with radiation efficiencies and resonating frequencies [2]. The relationship between the H_s variation and microstrip antenna performance is such that lower H_s generally perform better at high frequencies [3]. The lower H_s is applicable in higher-frequency applications, including a millimeter-wave (mm-wave) in the internet of things (IoT) and wearable devices [4]. Various substrates, including polyesters, textiles, and polymers with varying thicknesses and electrical properties, have been used in the antenna design [5].

However, the major challenge of designing a printable microstrip antenna is finding a suitable substrate and thickness with suitable dielectric constants. Changing the H_s affects the capacitance, effective dielectric constant, and inductive properties, causing a shift in the resonant frequency [6]. A substrate with a lower dielectric constant ($\epsilon_r=2.2, 3, \text{ or } 4$) achieved a wider bandwidth of the operating mm-wave frequency with a high gain, while a high dielectric constant of $\epsilon_r=10.2$ leads to an increase in surface wave loss and dielectric loss [7]. A polymer-based substrate such as polyimide (PI) has been considered for low-profile antennas due to its lightweight and better performance [8]. PI has a low dielectric permittivity with a reduced dielectric constant to improve circuit integration [9]. A printable antenna using a thin H_s exhibits a broad

frequency range and high performance [10]. A thin substrate has been reported to improve antenna bandwidth and efficiency at high frequencies due to its dielectric permittivity [11].

A study investigates the design of antennas by stacking four different types of substrates to improve the antenna performance, in which thinner substrates lead to better performance [12]. An antenna array with a thin-film substrate significantly enhanced gain with a compact size [13]. The PI thin substrate is low-cost compared to thicker substrates in producing a low-cost antenna [14]. A fabricated microstrip antenna on a thin PI substrate decreased antenna weight by up to 92% compared to a thicker substrate antenna [15]. A thin PI substrate improved antenna bandwidth for wideband applications [16]. A PI substrate with varying thicknesses is proposed in this research work due to its flexibility, lightweight, and low power consumption. This article applied regression modeling to investigate the effect of Hs variation on the antenna performance using the regression models and the models' equations.

Different regression models include nonlinear, linear, multiple linear, and polynomial regression models. The model design depends on the dependent and independent variables (x and y). The x variable predicts the response of y . Several recent studies [17]–[20] illustrated the regression in (1)–(15) with the various methods. This article worked on polynomial regression and developed the proposed regression models that analyzed the relationship between dependent and independent variables.

$$Y \approx \beta_0 + \beta_1 X \quad (1)$$

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x + \dots + \beta_n x + \epsilon \quad (3)$$

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x^2 + \dots + \beta_n x^n + \epsilon \quad (4)$$

The y is the dependent variable, x is the independent variable, and x predicts the y response. β_0 is the y -intercept, and β_i is the regression coefficient on the vertical axis of the regression line, which is the slope of the regression line. ϵ represented the random error and expressed the random factors' effect on the dependent variable. \approx represents approximately, and (4) represents the polynomial equation.

$$\hat{y} = \hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\beta}_1 X + \epsilon \quad (5)$$

$$\hat{\beta}_1 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{\beta}_0 = \bar{y} - \hat{\beta}_1 \bar{x} \quad (7)$$

$$\epsilon = \tilde{X}\tilde{\beta} - y \quad (8)$$

\hat{y} represents a prediction of Y where X represents x and the hat symbol denotes the estimated value for unknown parameters or coefficients in the predicted value of the response. The regression techniques will evaluate β_0 and β_i and observe the sample (x_i, y_i) to the model parameters and the scatter diagram. The determination coefficients (Coef) are in (9) and (10).

$$RSS = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y})^2 \quad (9)$$

$$RSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-2} RSS} \quad (10)$$

RSS is a regression sum of squares, and RSE measures fitness, indicating whether the model fits or does not fit the data. The predicted value \hat{y} is the original value of y . The Coef determined R-Square ($R-Sq$) analyzes the regression data of model performance and the strength of the relationship between the model and the data. The range of $R-Sq$ is between 0 and 1. The higher value of $R-Sq$ indicates the model to be optimal.

$$R - Sq = 1 - \frac{SS_{Error}}{SS_{Total}} \quad (11)$$

$$SS_{Error} = \sum_i (t_i - y_i)^2 \quad (12)$$

$$SS_{Total} = \sum_i (t_i - \bar{t}_i)^2 \quad (13)$$

SS_{Error} is the sum of the residual squares from the model, and SS_{Total} is the sum of squares of errors of the actual output and the mean of the output.

Since $R-Sq$ determines the fitness of data on the regression model, the model performance, the adjusted $R-Sq$ or modified $R-Sq$, is called $R-Sq$ adjust, which increases with the increased model performance. When unimportant features are added to the model and the residual error is reduced, the R-square adjustment ($R-Sq(adj)$) will also be reduced, and the R-Sq will increase.

$$R - Sq(adj) = 1 - \frac{(1-R-Sq)(N_V-1)}{N_V-N-1} \quad (14)$$

$$r = \sqrt{(R - Sq)r} \quad (15)$$

where N_V represents the number of the data sample, N is the number of features, making the $R-Sq(adj)$ more robust to the change of features, and r is the model correlation.

This article aims to address the issues of drawbacks in the 28 GHz printable microstrip antenna's parameters performance, such as resonant frequency (F_r), bandwidth (BW), gain (G), and efficiency (η) caused by the variation of H_s . To investigate, analyze, evaluate, and validate the experimental results and the regression models' equations. The proposed model and mathematical model equations were used to give insight to the antenna designers on how to enhance the antenna's parameters and the overall antenna's performance.

2. METHOD

2.1. Antenna design and configuration

The antenna design and configuration used a coplanar waveguide (CPW) with two slots on the patch and a gap between the feedline and the patch, as illustrated in Figure 1. The substrate thickness was varied to analyze the impact of PI substrate thicknesses (H_s) on the antenna's performance. Understanding the dielectric material is necessary since the dielectric material has a significant role in the antenna performance. The proposed antenna has a dielectric constant of $\epsilon_r=3.5$ and a loss tangent, $\delta=0.0027$, designed with various substrate thicknesses. The variation of H_s has a significant impact on the antenna's performance. The slotted CPW printable antenna with a compact size of $5 \times 5 \times 0.125 \text{ mm}^3$ was designed and fabricated. The antenna has a bidirectional radiation pattern suitable for IoT and biomedical applications. It has a bandwidth of (26.200 GHz - 30.242 GHz) with a return loss (RL) of 22.62 dB and achieved a gain of 3.81 dBi and 96.21% efficiency. Table 1 shows the proposed antenna dimensions, and Figure 1 shows the proposed antenna design. The impact of H_s variation on these parameters was investigated, analyzed, evaluated, and validated by the simulated and measured results and regression modeling.

Figure 1. Proposed 28 GHz microstrip antenna

Table 1. Antenna dimensions

Parameter	Ls	Ws	Mt	Hs	Lf	Wp	Lp	Wf	g	L	W
Dimension (mm)	5	5	0.035	0.125	2.15	3.1	1.95	0.4	0.15	1.00	0.95

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Simulated result and discussion

The simulated results in Figures 2(a) to (d) illustrate the effect of varying H_s on the frequency response characteristics. The Figure 2 show the simulated result with various H_s values ranging from (a) 0.025 mm to 0.075 mm, (b) 0.100 mm to 0.150 mm, (c) 0.175 mm to 0.225 mm, and (d) 0.250 mm to 0.300 mm at which the frequencies resonated. The results demonstrated how H_s variation causes a shift in center frequency, BW and RL.

Generally, the results in Table 2 show that the lower the H_s , the higher the η , while the higher the H_s , the lower the η . And the thicker the substrate, the higher the BW and G, but a thinner substrate of 0.025 mm to 0.125 mm leads to good impedance matching. These resulted in an improvement in the BW and G from 3.6 GHz to 5.54 GHz and from 3.8 dBi to 3.91 dBi, respectively.

Figure 2. Frequency response characteristics on the following substrate thickness: (a) 0.025 mm to 0.075 mm, (b) 0.100 mm to 0.150 mm, (c) 0.175 mm to 0.225 mm, and (d) 0.250 mm to 0.300 mm

Table 2. Effect of substrate thickness on the antenna parameters

No.	H_s (mm)	Fr (GHz)	Operating bands (GHz)	BW(GHz)	% BW (GHz)	RL (dB)	Gain (dBi)	Dir (dB)	η (%)
1	0.025	31.753	28.541-34.164	5.54	17.45	21.46	3.91	3.98	98.24
2	0.050	30.084	28.541-34.084	5.62	18.68	28.67	3.89	3.97	97.98
3	0.075	29.052	27.44-32.114	4.67	16.07	36.19	3.87	3.97	97.48
4	0.100	28.448	26.477-30.979	4.50	15.82	33.86	3.85	3.97	96.98
5	0.125	28.000	26.200-30.242	4.04	14.43	22.62	3.81	3.96	96.21
6	0.150	27.555	26.004-29.600	3.60	13.06	24.46	3.80	3.96	95.96
7	0.175	27.194	25.462-29.173	3.71	13.64	25.93	3.79	3.97	95.47
8	0.200	26.867	25.14-28.777	3.64	13.55	27.18	3.79	3.97	95.47
9	0.225	26.600	24.587-28.164	3.58	13.46	28.74	3.80	3.98	95.48
10	0.250	26.391	24.41-28.164	3.75	14.21	30.04	3.79	3.98	95.23
11	0.275	26.172	24.171-27.917	3.75	14.33	30.59	3.80	3.99	95.24
12	0.300	25.999	23.995-27.75	3.76	14.46	31.24	3.80	4.00	95.00
13	0.325	25.844	23.839-27.559	3.72	14.39	32.05	3.80	4.01	94.76
14	0.350	25.705	23.684-27.404	3.72	14.47	32.84	3.81	4.02	94.78
15	0.375	25.585	23.58-27.283	3.70	14.46	33.64	3.82	4.03	94.79
16	0.400	25.481	23.425-27.179	3.75	14.72	35.00	3.81	4.05	94.07
17	0.425	25.360	23.079-27.024	3.95	15.58	35.30	3.83	4.06	94.33
18	0.450	25.261	22.975-26.851	3.88	15.36	35.59	3.84	4.08	94.12
19	0.475	25.204	22.906-26.747	3.84	15.24	36.19	3.85	4.09	94.13
20	0.500	25.135	22.837-26.644	3.81	15.16	35.74	3.85	4.11	93.67
21	0.525	25.026	22.711-26.577	3.87	15.46	36.22	3.89	4.13	94.19
22	0.550	24.995	22.672-26.595	3.92	15.68	36.65	3.91	4.15	94.22
23	0.575	24.904	22.604-26.455	3.85	15.46	36.80	3.93	4.18	94.02
24	0.600	24.857	22.589-26.425	3.84	15.45	35.00	3.93	4.20	93.57
25	0.625	24.823	22.537-26.339	3.80	15.31	31.23	3.95	4.21	93.82
26	0.650	24.772	22.435-26.305	3.87	15.62	30.65	3.97	4.24	93.63
27	0.675	24.721	22.384-26.288	3.90	15.78	30.75	4.01	4.26	94.13
28	0.700	24.670	22.367-26.237	3.87	15.69	30.35	4.03	4.29	93.94
29	0.725	24.636	22.265-26.169	3.90	15.83	29.27	4.05	4.31	93.97
30	0.750	24.585	22.214-26.135	3.92	15.94	29.42	4.08	4.34	94.01

The antenna achieved a peak gain of 3.81 dBi, a BW of (26.200 GHz - 30.242 GHz), and an average radiation η of 96.21% at the 28 GHz center frequency on the Hs 0.125 mm. The antenna achieved a better BW and radiation η compared with the other related works, as shown in Table 3. The bidirectional radiation pattern enables the antenna for mm-wave applications for wearable devices. These made the antenna be placed in either the front or back position. Table 2 shows the data obtained from the simulation results, which were used to develop the proposed regression models' equations to analyze and evaluate the effect of Hs variation on Fr, G, % BW, RL, and η .

Table 3. Comparison of other work with the proposed design

Ref.	Fr GHz	Sub. type	Sub ϵ_r	Sub. $\tan \delta$	Size (mm ²)	SH (mm)	BW (GHz)	Gain (dBi)	η (%)
[21]	28	FR4	4.40	0.0200	7×7	0.800	2.620	6.59	82.08
[22]	28	PI	3.50	0.0027	5.19×4.73	0.270	1.427	5.33	86.00
[23]	28	Rogers RT6002	2.94	-	6×8	1.520	1.410	3.12	89.25
[24]	28	Rogers RT 4003	3.55	-	12×12	0.240	4.500	4.50	94.00
[25]	28	Polypropylene	2.34	0.0010	-	0.100	0.500	5.14	-
[26]	28	RT Duroid 5880	2.20	0.0040	5×4.4	0.500	0.850	1.00	90.00
This work	28	PI	3.50	0.0027	5×5	0.125	4.710	3.81	96.41

3.2. Fabrication result and discussion

A sputtering machine deposits silver ink on a PI substrate to print the proposed antenna. The one-layer printing process, which used a conductor thickness of one micrometer (1 μm) per round, lacked the required conductivity. Depositing additional layers of paste ink in the printed area has improved the conductivity. The antenna prototype was fabricated and tested to evaluate the validity of the simulated result. The process is cost-effective and safe to use, as the silver ink is toxin-free for the lungs and skin. The printed antenna maintains flexibility without cracking the ink surface, even at the possible maximum bending radius. Figure 3(a) illustrate the proposed antenna prototype, and Figure 3(b) the return loss (reflection coefficient) of S₁₁ parameters, simulated and measured results. Figures 4(a) and (b) illustrate the simulated and measured 2D radiation patterns for the H-plane and E-plane, respectively. The simulated and measured results are in good agreement, confirming their validity. The antenna's radiation η , BW, G, and bidirectional radiation pattern signify its suitability for the proposed mm-wave applications.

Figure 3. Fabricated antenna and its simulated and measured S₁₁: (a) antenna prototype and (b) S₁₁ performance

Figure 4. Simulated and measured 2D radiation patterns: (a) H plane and (b) E plane

3.3. Result analysis

The simulated results have demonstrated the impact of H_s variation on the frequency response characteristics. The average result illustrates how the average values of BW and G increased as the H_s increased and shifted to lower values as the H_s decreased. Generally, the result shows that the higher the H_s , the lower the F_r and η , and the lower the H_s , the higher the F_r and η . These indicate that thinner H_s increase the F_r and radiation η , which improves the antenna's performance. The illustration of a bidirectional radiation pattern enables the antenna to be placed in either the back or front positions. The PI substrate is a polymer-based material that has less power consumption, making the antenna ideal for mm-wave applications in IoT and wearable devices. The measured and simulated S-parameter, E, and H planes are in good agreement. Slightly disturbed due to conductor and dielectric effects, causing impedance mismatches that slightly affected the fabricated results, but they are still in good correlation. Future work needs to investigate the impact of H_s variation on the radiation patterns and impedance matching on the microstrip antenna's performance.

3.4. Comparative analysis

The proposed antenna achieved a wider BW and higher radiation η compared with the other related articles reported in the literature, as shown in the summary in comparison Table 3. The improvement is primarily attributed to the selection of a suitable thin H_s , which enhanced both radiation η and BW. This has made the microstrip antenna suitable for the proposed mm-wave applications. The measured and simulated results in this research work are correlated, confirming the validity of the results.

4. DEVELOPMENT OF MATHEMATICAL MODEL

4.1. Model design

The data (simulation result) was used to develop the proposed model equations using the MINITAB software. The H_s is the predictor variable, while the F_r , G, % BW, RL, and η are the response variables. Many models were developed in linear, quadratic, and cubic forms and analyzed, evaluated, and validated. The model with the least residual value on the fitted line plots and residual plots indicates the model's fitness to the data and is considered the proposed regression model. And the model is validated by checking the significance of the model coefficients, $R-Sq$ and $R-Sq(adj)$, and testing the hypotheses' P-value. The $R-Sq$ and $R-Sq(adj)$ values closer to 1 and the P-value less than the significance level α (0.05) indicate the model validity. The proposed models are to investigate the impact of the predictor variable (H_s) on the response variables (F_r , G, BW, RL, and η). Figure 5 illustrates the flow chart of the model design procedures.

Figure 5. Flow chart

4.2. Model testing

The proposed regression models were tested for their validity and acceptability. Hypotheses (P-value) and $R-Sq$ were tested to determine the fitness and validity of the models. The $R-sq$ value is between 0 and 1; the $R-sq$ value that is closer to 1, and the P-value is less than 0.05, indicating the model's fitness and validity [27]. The developed models achieved the following results: $R-sq$ values are 94.6%, 72.1%, 97.9%, 41.5%, and 96.1% for the F_r , % BW, G, RL, and η , respectively. These results indicate the validity of the models except the RL

model, whose value is closer to zero, 41% (0.41), which indicates insufficient evidence to conclude the model’s validity. Still, the RL model P-value is 0.00, indicating the model’s fitness and validity. The P-value of all the developed models is less than 0.05, except that of % BW, whose P-value is 0.059, indicating insufficient evidence to validate the model fitness. It does not evaluate the overall model’s fitness. Thus, the % BW *R-Sq* value is 0.72, signifying the model’s fitness and acceptability. We can, therefore, conclude that all the proposed models are validated. Table 4 summarizes the models’ performance and shows the correlation between the dependent and independent variables. Figures 6(a) to (e) and Figures 7(a) to (e) illustrate the impact of *H_s* on the fitted line plots; the straight lines indicate the proposed model, while the dotted lines indicate the data (CST-simulated result).

Table 4. The Summary of the model performance

Regression fitness	<i>S</i>	<i>R – Sq</i>	<i>R – Sq(adj)</i>	<i>r</i>
Center frequency	0.425860	94.6%	94.2%	0.97
Percentage bandwidth	0.640043	72.1%	68.9%	0.85
Gain	0.012882	97.9%	97.7%	0.99
Return loss	3.345330	41.5%	37.1%	0.64
Efficiency	0.263875	96.1%	95.9%	0.98

Figure 6. Fitted plot: (a) substrate thickness versus center frequency, (b) substrate thickness versus percentage bandwidth, (c) substrate thickness versus return loss, (d) substrate thickness versus gain, and (e) substrate thickness versus efficiency

Figure 7. Residual plots of four-in-one as a function of fitted values: (a) resonant frequency, (b) percentage bandwidth, (c) return loss, (d) gain, and (e) efficiency

4.3. Developed equation

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) on the developed polynomial regression models and the correlation between the data and the developed regression models. The proposed models' (16), (18), and (20) are quadratic, while (17) and (19) are cubic. The developed regression models were analyzed using the MINITAB software. In the proposed equations, the negative coefficients on the H_s indicate that the average responses of the antenna parameters (Fr, G, % BW, RL, and η) increase as the H_s decreases, and the positive coefficient indicates a decrease in the response variable as the H_s increases. The proposed equations can provide accurate information for a fast solution to filtering the design parameters. To avoid the computational cost and produce a low-profile antenna.

$$\text{Resonant Frequency (GHz)} = 30.71 - 20.45H_s + 17.28H_s^2 \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Percentage bandwidth (GHz)} = 18.79 - 43.20H_s + 115.5H_s^2 - 85.62H_s^3 \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Gain (dBi)} = 32.908 - 0.7730H_s + 1.356H_s^2 \quad (18)$$

$$\text{Return loss (dB)} = 28.13 - 23.12H_s + 169.7H_s^2 - 187.7H_s^3 \quad (19)$$

$$\text{Efficiency (\%)} = 98.31 - 15.13H_s + 12.78H_s^2 \quad (20)$$

4.4. ANOVA on the fitness of the developed model

The ANOVA table determines the performance of the developed models, evaluates and validates the results, and determines the significance of the models. To assess the models' fitness to the data provided and to validate the fitted line and residual plots of the models. Tables 5 and 6 present the ANOVA results for the model

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fitness and acceptability. When the P-value is <0.05 , the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, signifying that the model fits the data; for the P-value >0.05 , the H_0 is accepted, meaning that the model does not fit the data [27].

Table 5. ANOVA on the model fitness

Predictor versus response variables	Source	Regression	Residual error	Total
Resonant frequency versus substrate thickness	DF	1	28	29
	SS	70.116	20.548	90.664
	MS	70.116	0.734	
	F	95.54		
	p	0.000		
Percentage bandwidth versus substrate thickness	DF	3	26	29
	SS	27.5305	10.6510	38.1815
	MS	9.17684	0.40965	
	F	22.40		
	P-value	0.000		
Return loss versus substrate thickness	DF	2	27	29
	SS	214.092	302.163	516.256
	MS	107.046	107.046	
	F	9.57		
	P-value	0.001		
Gain versus substrate thickness	DF	2	27	29
	SS	0.204666	0.004481	0.209147
	MS	0.102333	0.000166	
	F	616.62		
	P-value	0.000		
Efficiency versus substrate thickness	DF	2	27	29
	SS	46.9208	1.8800	48.8008
	MS	23.4604	0.0696	
	F	336.93		
	P-value	0.000		

Table 6. Sequential ANOVA

Predictor versus response variables	Source	Linear	Quadratic	Cubic
Resonant frequency versus substrate thickness	DF	1	1	
	SS	70.1159	15.6513	
	F	95.54		
	p	0.000	0.000	
	P-value	0.590	0.001	0.000
Percentage bandwidth versus substrate thickness	DF	1	1	1
	SS	0.4002	13.3687	13.7616
	F	0.30	14.79	33.59
	P-value	0.590	0.001	0.000
	P-value	0.021	0.003	0.012
Return loss versus substrate thickness	DF	1	1	1
	SS	90.804	123.288	66.111
	F	5.98	11.02	7.28
	P-value	0.021	0.003	0.012
	P-value	0.000	0.000	0.000
Gain versus substrate thickness	DF	1	1	
	SS	0.108280	0.096386	
	F	30.06	580.79	
	P-value	0.000	0.000	
	P-value	0.000	0.000	
Efficiency versus substrate thickness	DF	1	1	
	SS	38.3528	8.5680	
	F	102.78	123.05	
	P-value	0.000	0.000	
	P-value	0.000	0.000	

4.5. ANOVA on the sequential prediction

Table 7 shows ANOVA on sequential prediction; H_s predicts the response variables (Fr, BW, G, RL, and η). In the ANOVA table, T-values represent the standard errors of the regression coefficient, and a high T-value with the least P-value indicates that the model is of substantial significance. The Coef (coefficient) shows the direction and size of the relationship between the predictor and response variables. A positive Coef indicates a positive relationship, while a negative Coef indicates a negative relationship between the variables. This signifies that the negative Coef in H_s -values on the Fr and η relationship indicates a continuous decrease in the Fr and η values as H_s -values increase. SE Coef represents the standard error of the Coef; the higher SE Coef indicates less confidence in the predicted values, while the smaller SE Coef signifies a more precise prediction. A P-value less than the significance level (0.05) indicates a significant relationship between the predictor and response variable, and a P-value greater than the significance level of 0.05 indicates an insignificant

relationship between the variables. To confirm the model's precision and validity. The P-values of 0.000 and 0.021 signify the model's significance and acceptability, while the P-value of 0.059 indicates poor model fitness. A P-value greater than 0.05 indicates insufficient evidence to validate the model fitness and acceptability; it does not evaluate the overall model fitness and acceptability. The 4-in-one residual plots can further assess the regression model's fitness and acceptability.

Table 7. Sequential prediction ANOVA

Predictor versus response variables	Predictor	Constant	Hs
Resonant frequency versus substrate thickness	Coef	28.9270	-7.0651
	SE Coef	0.3208	0.7228
	T-value	90.17	-9.77
	P-value	0.000	0.000
Percentage bandwidth versus substrate thickness	Coef	14.9518	0.5337
	SE Coef	0.4350	0.9801
	T-value	34.37	0.54
	P-value	0.000	0.590
Return loss versus substrate thickness	Coef	28.340	8.040
	SE Coef	1.460	3.289
	T-value	19.41	2.44
	P-value	0.000	0.021
Gain versus substrate thickness	Coef	3.76775	0.27764
	SE Coef	0.02248	0.05064
	T-value	167.64	5.48
	P-value	0.000	0.000
Efficiency versus substrate thickness	Coef	96.9878	-5.2253
	SE Coef	0.2287	0.5154
	T-value	423.99	-10.14
	P-value	0.000	0.000

4.6. Residual plot

The residual plots include residual value versus data order, in which the mean values are zero (0) for the model to be valid. Figures 7(a) to (e) include a histogram of the residuals, which indicates the distribution of errors to assess whether the model is appropriate for the data, confirm the model's fitness, and its acceptability. The model errors are more on -1, 0, 1, -1, and -0.5 as shown in Figures 7 (a) to (e), respectively. These fall within the model error limit close to the trend line to signify the model's fitness and validity. The histogram residuals confirm the normality assumptions, as the mean values are approximately zero and the data points are within ± 2 standard errors, which corresponds to a 95% confidence interval. The standardized residuals, calculated from the regression standard errors, must be within the range of ± 2 , which is approximately 95% of the data points [28].

5. CONCLUSION

This research work simulated and fabricated a 28 GHz microstrip antenna and developed and proposed regression model equations to investigate and evaluate the impact of Hs variation on Fr, G, % BW, RL, and η . The fitted line plots analyzed the correlation between the data and the developed models. The antenna was printed on a flexible PI substrate using silver ink to avoid computational cost and fast solutions for filtering design parameters, which is the main objective of the proposed design. The models' equations and experimental results were validated. This was done by comparing the simulated and measured results and the ANOVA of the model characteristics. The measurement shows good agreement with the simulation results. The lower Hs achieved an improved BW and η , a low-cost and low-profile antenna for future mm-wave applications. The model equations can accurately and faster predict the antenna's parameters (Fr, BW, G, RL, and η) and overall antenna performance than many commercially available advanced simulation tools. This gives an insight into how antenna designers can predict the antenna's parameters and performance. These methods could reduce the cost of production and improve the antenna's optimum performance. This paper suggested that the regression models can be expanded to evaluate additional antenna parameters, such as radiation patterns and polarization, to enhance the antenna performance. It also meant the proposed design should be used in frequency-sensitive applications. This article is the first to use the polynomial regression model equations to evaluate the impact of Hs variation on the 28 GHz printable microstrip antenna to the best of our knowledge. The paper suggested extending the proposed regression modeling approach to evaluate additional parameters such as radiation patterns, polarization, and impedance-matching characteristics. It also suggested regression modeling to evaluate the impact of Hs on various parameters in the Terahertz frequencies. Moreover, it suggested that future

advancements in microstrip antenna technology should focus on modern integration techniques to optimize the overall antenna performance for future applications.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [Mohd Fadzil Ain], upon reasonable request.

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